

TEACHING BUSINESS ENGLISH FOR ENGLISH-MAJORED STUDENTS IN HUPI: MATERIAL SELECTION AND DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The article suggests how to select and develop the material of Business English to teach for English-majored students in HUPI. Also, it mentions the difference between teaching Business English and General English level, these might influence mainly on the course design, the teaching methods and skills which are acquired by the business English-majored students, as well as on the role performed by English lecturers in HUPI. Selecting and developing authentic materials and/ or coursebooks which can simplify and facilitate English-majored students' acquisition of Business English lexicon. That might be considered as the first step to succeed in that field.

Keywords: Business English, General English, material development, specific context, coursebook, ELT.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the economical, cultural, and social context has been a deep and wide integration and globalization and additionally relationships among countries in the world have become much closer than ever before. Especially, after the Free Trade Agreement (FTA) officially effects, Vietnam is getting one of the countries which attract the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in a region of ASEAN. Moreover, since April 2019, Vietnam has negotiated and signed successfully more than sixteen international trade agreements. With such opportunities, mastering at Business English is the advantage. Much better knowledge of Business English seems to be, next to managerial skills, a necessity nowadays. Business English is communication with other people with a specific context. However, to achieve competence in using Business English in a global environment requires a lot of factors from the aspects of Business English teaching and learning in centers, colleges and universities. HUPI is not an exception. Though Business English has been taught and learnt in educational institutes for years, it still cannot be denied the fact that its effects on English teaching in general and business development support in particular are not compatible with current potentials and requirements. Neither is Business English teaching and learning in HUPI. Especially, Business English teaching and learning in HUPI has been conducted since 2016 - the official establishment of Faculty of Foreign Languages. It has been over three years experiencing teaching and learning Business English in HUPI, a series of materials: Market Leader Pre-intermediate had been chosen which has been considered the authentic materials and well evaluated by English lecturers and Business English learners.

The Scope Of Teaching Business English

According to Brieger, 1997, Business English appeared on English language teaching stage as course program and learning objective in the late seventies, and has been shaped by a range of influences from both the ELT and non-ELT world. Its course content reflects the diverse needs of varied learner - groups and its pedagogic approaches have been impacted by the experiences of its learners – training. So, the teaching Business English has received noticeable contributions from:

- ELT methodologies which teach language knowledge and language skills in a range of business contexts through communicative activities
- communication training which develops the effectiveness of the total communication process by looking at the message in term of its form and delivery
- management disciplines which provide professional content on key areas.

In short, the teaching of Business English brings together three areas such as:

- teaching – pedagogic skills involved in running training program
- English – knowledge of the language and culture
- business – familiarity with the key issues facing specific learners.

The Objective Of Business English Learning and Teaching

As stated by Brieger, 1997 in the objectives of Business English learning and teaching it concluded the three elements or skills for any Business English course: Accuracy, Fluency, and Effectiveness, which contributed to the decision of course design, upon the specific context

Business English teaching contexts were presumed in general, to be found within three different environments: education institutes, private language schools, and companies, each of which was compatible with varied teaching requirements. It seems clear that, different contexts, learners and needs lead to the various curriculum for Business English teaching. Designing a Business English course is a complicated process of needs analysis, starting from the course aims and objectives, to syllabus components, the syllabus organization and finally, material selection and development (Frendo, 2005).

The Scope Of Business English

Corresponding with learner objectives, the two major elements as the building blocks for course design and a constellation of minor forces. Language knowledge reflects the formal aspects of grammar, vocabulary and the sound system. In communication, the knowledge to transmit messages through different channels, for example presentations, meetings, telephoning, or written documents, such as correspondence or reports. Language knowledge reflects what one knows of

the language, communication skills what one knows how to do with the language. Together they are a powerful instrument in assessing overall competence.

The legitimate scope of the pedagogic activities as Business English trainers is to design and deliver courses that aim to increase language knowledge and to develop communication skills (Brieger, 1997).

2 GENERAL ENGLISH VS BUSINESS ENGLISH

Previously, a number of key issues in the teaching and learning of Business English have been mentioned. Another aspect considering as pedagogic and classroom issue is General English. According to Brieger (1997), some contrasts between Business English and General English were tabled below:

Business English		General English
	Programs	
Focus on developing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – accuracy – fluency – effectiveness <i>Focus on developing:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – general and specialists language knowledge – general and professional communication skills 		<i>Focus on developing:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – accuracy – fluency <i>Focus on developing:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – general language knowledge – general communication skills
	Syllabus	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Set courses with fixed objectives and syllabus. – Special courses with special syllabus. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Often determined by choice of textbook and end-of-term examination. – Wide ranging syllabus: vocabulary

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – One-to-one courses may develop syllabus and content on an ongoing basis. 		<p>from different areas and different styles</p>
	Trainers	
<p><i>Need the following mix of knowledge and skills</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – communication skills training – knowledge of business content 		<p><i>Need the following mix of knowledge and skills</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – ELT methodology
	Methodology	
<p><i>Based on:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – communicative ELT methodology – communication skills training 		<p><i>Based on:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – communicative ELT methodology
	Materials	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Off-the-shelf materials for business English but may not meet needs of group or course, then it may be necessary to develop materials for a specific course or to add authentic materials 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Wide choice of off-the-shelf material for general English for all the levels. Materials development not required by the teacher.
	Evaluation of progress	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – An off-the-shelf Business English test may be used by some organizations. – Informal assessment: emphasis on success of communication. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Formal oral and written examination evaluating accuracy, fluency and general communicative ability. – Informal assessment: accuracy, appropriacy of vocabulary and pronunciation.

3 BUSINESS ENGLISH TEACHING AND LEARNING IN HUFİ WITH A COURSEBOOK: MARKET LEADER PRE-INTERMEDIATE

Selecting And Developing Materials

There is a large range of different off-the-shelf language teaching publications available, and it might seem that all a teacher has to do is find those that best fit the needs and aims of their learners. Coursebooks are popular all over the world, and there are very good reasons for this. A coursebook provides a solid framework to work with, and it is useful for less experienced teacher or one who is under pressure. Most coursebooks look professional, which is normally important with

business English learners. (Frendo, 2005). Currently, the framed program for business English-major students has been designed six (6) credits that are divided into two semesters and scheduled in the second year. The coursebook selecting and developing to teach business English-major students is Market Leader, pre-intermediate. The coursebook of Market Leader is a multi-level business English course for business people and students of business English. It has been developed in association with the Financial Times and Pearson Longman, one of the leading sources of business information in the world. It consists of 12 units based on topics of great interest to everyone involved in international business. It includes comprehensive teacher's guides and resources for the students, self-study materials, audio, and video, etc.,. Each unit contains qualified contents, proper and real knowledge. The four language skills Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing always combined together in all units of lessons. Moreover, each unit content helps Business English learners improve all comprehensive skills. Much business vocabulary will be enriched through the extracts and articles from Financial Times. Besides, Business English learners can upgrade soft skills, solve problems through genuine case studies. Effective business English materials need to allow learners to produce language they will need in their workplace, and these activities need to be designed into the course. Typically, such activities involve role-play, simulations and/or case studies. (Frendo, 2005). The author of this article, who has been applying this coursebook for teaching business English for students of business English, prefers such case studies. Students are assigned to work in groups and give their presentations in front of class. Surprisingly, most of the students are very excited and interested in working like this. Because they have a chance to improve comprehensive skills. This Market Leader Pre-intermediate level that features completely updated content and a significantly enhanced range of authentic resource material, reflecting the latest trends in the business world. The course will significantly improve your ability to communicate in English in a wide range of business situations and develop the communication skills to succeed in business and will enlarge the knowledge of the business world. Everybody studying this course will become more fluent and confident in using the language of business and should increase their career prospects.

The Business English Teacher

Evan Frendo (2005) stated that Business English teachers need to be able to make informed decisions about language and language learning. Also, they need credibility, professionalism, and an awareness of the business world. Above all, they must be willing, themselves, to learn. Teaching Business English is considered to inherently differ from Teaching General English, something that has been made evident by considering the different words used to describe Business English teachers. Many teachers in the field of Business English call themselves trainers, coaches, or even consultants. These descriptions extend the meaning of the traditional teaching job and draw attention to the variety of different expectations for Business English teachers.

Teacher as trainer

According to Frendo, 2005, there is a difference between teacher and trainer. A teacher whose task is to educate someone so that they can have more chance at succeeding in life. Meanwhile, a trainer who is required to change a person's behavior or ability so that they can do a specific job. Training is job-oriented, while teaching is person-oriented. Thus, the trainer's aim is to develop certain skills by trained employees, to help them to adjust themselves better to the working conditions in the company and to be more efficient in their work.

Teacher as coach

A coach is someone who can help the learner take advantage of the learning opportunities in their own working environment and show the learner of business English how to learn in an autonomous way. More importantly, it involves helping the learner to better understand his/her own strengths and weaknesses, and plan accordingly.

Teacher as consultant

Evan Frendo (2005), a consultant is an expert who is brought in because his or her skills or know-how are not available in the company. In the Business English Teaching process, it can thus refer to very different areas: analyzing communication needs, involving the teacher in negotiations while looking for the best course location. A qualified Business English teacher has to own high proficiency in the target language, field of specific language and especially an ability to select, develop and/or prepare adequate materials. To sum up, besides good materials, Business English teacher in any role is always an inspiration and motivation which can push learners to indulge in the subject of Business English. So the relationship between teacher and learner in Business English courses should be much closer to achieve the goals of the subject.

4 CONCLUSION

It seems obvious that English has become not only the language of communication worldwide but also the language of science, technology and commerce. The current position of English as the main language used for international communication means that it is essential for communication amongst the operators of the global market. Business English is becoming a reality. And from now on, business English teaching and learning in centers, colleges and universities have been seriously considered. Many factors bring success to business English. One of them is how to select and develop materials and also a need to change the teaching methods to adapt to the trends. The role of Business English teacher must be much considered. So, I hope with aspiring and motivating business professionals possessing knowledge skills of business English will become effective and competitive in the global market.

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